

Value of Exclusion Zones as a Fisheries Management Tool in Europe

A strategic evaluation and the development of an analytical framework (QLK5-CT1999-01271)

Final Report

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Case Study 1: The Gulf of Castellammare, Sicily, Italy¹

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